

MICROWAVE MEASUREMENT OF SEA SURFACE
VELOCITIES FROM PIER AND AIRCRAFT

W. C. Keller and W. J. Plant
U.S. Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, D.C. 20375

J. W. Johnson
NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, VA 23665

Abstract

Illumination of the ocean surface with coherent microwave radiation allows one to measure the mean velocity of the surface area via Doppler shifts. If the illuminated area is small compared to dominant ocean waves then in addition to mean currents, fluctuating surface velocities due to the waves can be detected. In this paper we present such measurements made during the ARSLOE experiment both from the CERC Field Research Facility pier at Duck, N.C. and from aircraft flying over the ocean east of Duck. Time averaged velocities determined from microwave Doppler measurements from the pier showed good agreement with currents measured by following dye tracers. Fluctuating parts of these signals were used to infer wave height spectra which were compared with spectra from standard Baylor gauges and found to agree well. Similar Doppler shift fluctuations were observed in signals obtained from aircraft measurements and were shown to agree well with surface wave data from an underlying buoy. These techniques promise to produce new methods for measuring waves and currents from stationary and moving platforms.

1. Introduction

In 1978, Plant, et.al. reported a coherent, single-frequency, microwave technique which was capable of measuring sea surface velocities over surface areas of a few square meters. (Plant et.al., 1978). Subsequent work has shown that wave height spectra comparable to those from conventional wave gauges can be deduced from surface velocities measured over such small areas. (Plant and Schuler, 1980; Plant et.al., 1982).

In this paper we report measurements made with this technique from the pier at the CERC Field Research Facility at Duck, N.C. and from P-3 aircraft flying just east of this pier. We show that mean surface currents determined by this method compare well with currents measured using floating dyes. We offer additional confirmation that the technique can be employed on a fixed platform to produce viable wave height spectra if the wave direction is known. Finally, we show that wave-induced surface velocities may be measured from aircraft using this technique. Most of the measurements reported here were made as part of the 1980 ARSLOE experiment. Wave height spectra measured from the pier were obtained two years earlier, however.

2. Description of Technique

The technique as it is applied from a fixed platform has been described in some detail in earlier papers. (Plant et.al., 1978; Plant and Schuler, 1980). Here we shall content ourselves with outlining the basic equations and mentioning briefly how they are modified when applied to moving platforms. Measurements described here were made with CW L-, X-, or K_u- Band coherent microwave systems which illuminated patches of the ocean surface small compared to dominant ocean wavelengths as shown in Figure 1.

Geometry of the coherent microwave technique
Figure 1

These systems viewed the surface at angles for which the backscatter is given by composite surface theory. Thus the scatter is primarily caused by short waves, or Bragg scatterers, which are advected by currents as well as by orbital velocities set up by longer waves. Over the small illuminated surface area, these large-scale velocities may be considered to be constant. Thus, beating the backscattered signal down to audio frequencies produces a signal whose frequency f_{out} is variable and may be described by

$$f_{out} = f_a + \vec{k}_0 \cdot (\vec{c} + \vec{u} + \vec{u}_c) / \pi \quad (1)$$

Where f_a is an audio offset frequency, \vec{k}_0 is the microwavenumber, c is the Bragg wave phase speed, \vec{u} is the large wave orbital velocity, and \vec{u}_c is the surface current. This frequency is easily

measured by amplifying the signal, clipping it, and feeding it through an f/V converter to produce a voltage. Taking zero voltage to correspond to the frequency f_a , the output voltage is

$$V_{out} = 2a\{(c + u_c + u)\cos\theta + v \sin\theta\}/\lambda_0 \quad (2)$$

Where θ is the grazing angle, λ_0 is the microwave wavelength, u and u_c are the horizontal components of orbital velocity and surface current along the antenna-look direction, and v is the vertical component of orbital velocity. The constant a is the calibration factor of the f/V converter in volts/Hz.

Since u and v are random variables with zero mean, a long-time average of Eq. (2) yields the mean surface current along the horizontal antenna direction:

$$\bar{u}_c = (\lambda_0 \overline{V_{out}} / 2a \cos\theta) + c. \quad (3)$$

Here, c may be either positive or negative depending on the direction of travel of the Bragg wave. In these experiments, we took it to be positive when the antenna pointed within 60° of downwind and negative for antenna directions within 60° of upwind. For crosswind conditions, c was taken to be zero on the assumption that the two signs would cancel under such conditions.

The power spectrum of V_{out} shows a peak in the vicinity of the dominant ocean wave due to u and v . In the case of stationary platforms, it is straightforward to show that this spectrum is related to the variance spectrum of the ocean waves $E(f)$ by

$$E(f) = \frac{\lambda_0^2 \tanh^2 Kd G_{vv}(f)}{16\pi^2 a^2 f^2 (\sin^2\theta \tanh^2 Kd + \cos^2\phi \cos^2\theta)} \quad (4)$$

where f is long wave frequency, K is its wave-number, d is the water depth, $G_{vv}(f)$ is the power spectral density of V_{out} , and ϕ is the angle between antenna-look and wave directions.

For a moving platform, the frequency in Eq. (4) is that of the ocean wave in the frame of reference of the platform, i.e., the encounter frequency f_e , given by

$$f_e = f + \vec{K} \cdot \vec{U} = \vec{K} \cdot (\vec{C} + \vec{U}) \quad (5)$$

where C is the long wave phase speed and \vec{U} is platform velocity. Thus for a spectrum of ocean waves a transformation from f_e to f must be performed to finally obtain the ocean wave spectrum in an earth-fixed frame of reference. In this

paper, we shall limit ourselves to displaying the spectrum

$$O(f_e) = \lambda_0^2 G_{vv}(f_e)/4a^2 \quad (6)$$

a line-of-sight velocity spectrum, for our aircraft data.

3. Pier Measurements

During ARSLOE, an X-Band microwave system (9.375 GHz) was mounted on the CERC pier looking along the shore line. Components of current parallel to the shore line were measured with this system and are displayed for the period of October 2 and 3, 1980 in Figure 2. Also shown in

Currents measured by radar and dye along with wind parameters.
Figure 2

this figure are wind speed and direction as measured by an anemometer mounted beside the microwave antenna. Shortly before the period displayed in this figure, the wind direction had shifted to the south. Thus early current measurements show the current changing to flow from the south as it lags the change in wind direction. Error bars in this figure are indicative of the width of the microwave Doppler spectrum. Note the good agreement between the current as measured by the microwave system and by floating dye on the morning of October 3.

Measurements had previously been made from the end of the CERC pier with this type of microwave system, but operating at L-Band (1.5 GHz), in order to measure wave height spectra. Figure 3 shows a comparison between $E(f)$ as measured by this system and by a Baylor gauge located near the end of the pier. Peak frequencies of the spectra and spectral shapes agree quite well.

Variance spectra of ocean waves measured with a coherent radar and a Baylor gauge.
Figure 3

Spectral densities at the peak vary somewhat but variations between consecutive Baylor gauge spectra are greater than those between microwave and Baylor gauge spectra. The wind speed on September 3 was about 6 m/sec and on September 13 was about 12 m/sec.

4. Aircraft Measurements

Microwave systems similar to those operated from the pier were flown on NRL and NASA P-3 aircraft during ARSLOE. These systems were called ROWS for Remote Ocean Wave Spectrometer. Figure 4 shows the configuration of these aircraft systems. The systems were flown at low altitudes (200-400 m) so that the azimuthal footprint of the antennas was typically smaller than an ocean wavelength.

ROWS configurations on aircraft.
NRL: 9.375 GHz, $\phi_B = 23$, $\theta_B = 0.9$.
NASA: 13.9 GHz, $\phi_B = 25$, $\theta_B = 0.5$.
Figure 4

Backscattered signals to these systems showed frequency variations at rates which corresponded well to ocean wave frequencies. Figure 5 gives examples of the spectra $O(f_e)$ of these signals for data collected with the NASA K-Band (13.9 GHz) system on November 12, 1980. Spectra are shown for four different flight directions as given by the vector diagrams in each figure. Laser profilometer and buoy data showed a dominant ocean wavelength of 90 meters at the time these measurements were made. The arrows in Figure 5 indicate the expected encounter frequencies of a wave of this length for the different flight directions. As the figure shows, the frequencies of the observed spectral peaks agree quite well with these expected frequencies. The peaks in the upwave and downwave spectra are shifted by an amount which agrees well with the expected shift in Eq. (5) due to the phase speed of a 90 meter long wave. The large spectral density near zero frequency shows the effect of variable aircraft motion on the spectra. The wind speed on this day was 12.7 m/sec and the significant wave height indicated by laser and buoy was about 2.6 m.

Spectra $O(f_e)$ from the NASA ROWS system.
Figure 5

5. Conclusions

These experiments indicate that a simple, coherent, CW microwave system which measures sea surface velocities is capable of yielding accurate information on waves and currents when employed from a stationary platform. Detection of waves from moving platforms using such a system has also been demonstrated here. The feasibility of measuring directional wave spectra from aircraft using this technique seems promising but requires further investigation and, probably, recourse to pulsed methods.

6. Acknowledgements

This work was supported in part by the Naval Material Command as Subproject Number SF59-557. The authors wish to thank the Coastal Engineering Research Center for the Baylor gauge data and the National Data Buoy Office for access to buoy data.

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